

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part-XLII. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some New 1,3-Diaryl-2-(aryloxy)propan-1,3-diones

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In view of potential pharmacological activity exhibited by azo-compounds^{1,2}, it has been proposed to synthesise some new 1,3-diaryl-2-(aryloxy)propan-1,3-diones having different substituents in the phenyl rings for study of their antibacterial activities.

m-(1) and *p*-Nitrobenzaldehydes (2) (Scheme 1) were condensed with *p*-methyl- (3), ethyl- (4), methoxy- (5) and ethoxyacetophenones (6) in presence of sodium hydroxide when the corresponding styryl ketones (7-10 when X = *m*-NO₂; 11-14 when X = *p*-NO₂) were obtained. The nmr spectra of 7-14 were in accordance with the proposed structures. The olefinic protons (CO-CH=CH) appeared as clean doublets at δ 7.30 and 7.78 situated at positions of α and β respectively, confirming the condensation of the reactants. These styryl ketones (7-14) were separately treated with bromine in chloroform solution with stirring to yield the respective dibromides (15-18 when X = *m*-NO₂; 19-22 when X = *p*-NO₂). In the nmr spectrum, two diagnostic doublets at δ 5.60 and 5.70 for COCHBr and CHBr-Ar protons (α and β to keto) respectively, were indicative of bromination of the double bond adjacent to carbonyl functionality. The dibromides (15-22) on treatment with methanolic KOH on refluxing and subsequent acidification with HCl yielded the corresponding 1-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-methyl/ethyl/methoxy/ethoxyphenyl)propane-1,3-diones (23-26 when X = *m*-NO₂; 27-30 when X = *p*-NO₂): δ 6.75 (C=CH-C), 3.85 (methoxy protons).

In the last step of synthesis, the ice-cold (0-5°) diazotised solution of aromatic bases (aniline; *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidines; *o*-, *m*-, *p*-anisidines; *o*-, *m*-*p*-chloroanilines; *o*-, *m*-, *p*-bromoanilines; *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitroanilines) was slowly added to a stirred solution (0-5°) of compounds 23-30 to afford 2-aryloxy derivatives of 1,3-diarylpropane-1,3-diones (31-155): δ 6.8-8.5 (ArH), 6.54 (-CO-CH-CO), 4.02 (OCH₃), 2.48 (ArCH₃); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 667-1 637 (CO), 1 600-1 580 (N=N), 850, 750 (substituted phenyl), 860 (C-N), 1 500, 1 350 cm⁻¹ (NO₂, NO₂ assym and sym)³.

Experimental

m-Nitrobenzylidene-*p*-methylacetophenone (7): To a mixture of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1; 7.55 g, 0.05 mol) and *p*-methylacetophenone (3; 6.7 g, 0.05 mol) in ethanol (250 ml), aqueous NaOH (20 ml) was added slowly and stirred

for 3 h and then cooled in ice. The solid separated was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 128° (lit. 131°).

m-Nitrobenzylidene-*p*-methylacetophenone dibromide (15): Compound 7 (13.35 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of chloroform and bromine (3 ml) in chloroform (5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring and the contents left overnight. Chloroform was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (90%), m.p. 168° (lit. 170°).

1-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)propan-1,3-dione (23): To a solution of 15 (12.8 g, 0.03 mol) in methanol (200 ml) was added a solution of KOH (5.3 g) in methanol (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then chilled to deposit KBr which was filtered out and the filtrate after acidification with HCl yielded a solid which was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (70%), m.p. 155° (lit. 157°).

1-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)-2-(benzeneazo)propan-1,3-dione (31): To an ice-cold solution of 23 (0.57 g, 0.002 mol) in acetone (125 ml) containing sodium (12 g), was gradually added a diazotised solution of aniline (0.186 g, 0.002 mol) with stirring at 0-5°. The resulting solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (62%), m.p. 170° (Found: C, 68.0, H, 4.2. C₂₂H₁₇O₄N₃ requires: C, 68.2; H, 4.4%).

Other 1-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)-2-(aryloxy)propan-1,3-dione were similarly prepared: 32 (R = *o*-Me), m.p. 143°; 33 (*m*-Me), 136°; 34 (*p*-Me), 160°; 35 (*o*-MeO), 140°; 36 (*m*-MeO), 160°; 37 (*p*-MeO), 140°; 38 (*o*-Cl), 185°; 39 (*m*-Cl), 161°; 40 (*p*-Cl), 174°; 41 (*o*-Br), 155°; 42 (*m*-Br), 185°; 43 (*p*-Br), 181°; 44 (*o*-NO₂), 161°; 45 (*m*-NO₂), 171°; 46 (*p*-NO₂), 215°. Compounds (47-61) with X = *p*-NO₂, Y = *p*-Me: 47 (R = H), m.p. 137°; 48 (R = *o*-Me), 179°; 49 (*m*-Me), 158°; 50 (*p*-Me), 163°; 51 (*o*-MeO), 205°; 52 (*p*-MeO), 178°; 53 (*o*-Cl), 185°; 54 (*m*-Cl), 179°; 55 (*p*-Cl), 216°; 56 (*o*-Br), 212°; 57 (*m*-Br), 206°; 58 (*p*-Br), 221°; 59 (*o*-NO₂), 209°; 60 (*m*-NO₂), 196°; 61 (*p*-NO₂), 226°. Compounds (62-77) with X = *m*-NO₂; Y = *p*-Et: 62 (R = H), 134°; 63 (*o*-Me), 125°; 64 (*m*-Me), 138°; 65 (*p*-Me), 127°; 66 (*o*-MeO), 137°; 67 (*m*-MeO), 160°; 68 (*p*-MeO), 122°; 69 (*o*-Cl), 137°; 70 (*m*-Cl), 134°; 71 (*p*-Cl),

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156°; **72** (*o*-Br), 141°; **73** (*m*-Br), 166°; **74** (*p*-Br), 139°; **75** (*o*-NO₂), 144°; **76** (*m*-NO₂), 156°; **77** (*p*-NO₂), 172°. Compounds (**78-93**) having X = *p*-NO₂, Y = *p*-Et : **78** (R = H), m.p. 130°; **79** (*o*-Me), 145°; **80** (*m*-Me), 129°; **81** (*p*-Me),

154°; **82** (*o*-Me), 160°; **83** (*o*-Me), 145°; **84** (*p*-MeO), 159°; **85** (*o*-Cl), 154°; **86** (*m*-Cl), 129°; **87** (*p*-Cl), 194°; **88** (*o*-Br), 151°; **89** (*m*-Br), 172°; **90** (*p*-Br), 191°; **91** (*o*-NO₂), 175°; **92** (*m*-NO₂), 175°; **93** (*p*-NO₂), 212°. Compounds (**94-109**) having X = *m*-NO₂, Y = *p*-MeO : **94** (R = H), m.p. 171°; **95** (*o*-Me), 166°; **96** (*m*-Me), 163°; **97** (*p*-Me), 186°; **98** (*o*-MeO), 163°; **99** (*m*-MeO), 190°; **100** (*p*-MeO), 130°; **101** (*o*-Cl), 187°; **102** (*m*-Cl), 170°; **103** (*p*-Cl), 189°; **104** (*o*-Br), 179°; **105** (*m*-Br), 183°; **106** (*p*-Br), 199°; **107** (*o*-NO₂), 161°; **108** (*m*-NO₂), 213°; **109** (*p*-NO₂), 209°. Compounds (**110-123**) having X = *p*-NO₂, Y = *p*-MeO : **110** (R = H), m.p. 164°; **111** (*o*-Me), 188°; **112** (*m*-Cl), 156°; **113** (*o*-MeO), 209°; **114** (*m*-MeO), 149°; **115** (*o*-Cl), 189°; **116** (*m*-Cl), 193°; **117** (*p*-Cl), 197°; **118** (*o*-Br), 204°; **119** (*m*-Br), 177°; **120** (*p*-Br), 205°; **121** (*o*-NO₂), 173°; **122** (*m*-NO₂), 205°; **123** (*p*-NO₂), 182°. Compounds (**124-139**) having X = *m*-NO₂, Y = *p*-EtO : **124** (R = H), m.p. 157°; **125** (*o*-Me), 152°; **126** (*m*-Me), 137°; **127** (*p*-Me), 178°; **128** (*o*-MeO), 169°; **129** (*m*-MeO), 155°; **130** (*p*-MeO), 130°; **131** (*o*-Cl), 165°; **132** (*m*-Cl), 163°; **133** (*p*-Cl), 205°; **134** (*o*-Br), 169°; **135** (*m*-Br), 154°; **136** (*p*-Br), 211°; **137** (*o*-NO₂), 155°; **138** (*m*-NO₂), 185°; **139** (*p*-NO₂), 234°. Compounds (**140-155**) having X = *p*-NO₂, Y = *p*-EtO : **140** (R = H), m.p. 154°; **141** (*o*-Me), 148°; **142** (*m*-Me), 151°; **143** (*p*-Me), 157°; **144** (*o*-MeO), 177°; **145** (*m*-MeO), 132°; **146** (*p*-MeO), 160°; **147** (*o*-Cl), 166°; **148** (*m*-Cl), 167°; **149** (*p*-Cl), 152°; **150** (*o*-Br), 164°; **151** (*m*-Br), 170°; **152** (*p*-Br), 157°; **153** (*o*-NO₂), 187°; **154** (*m*-NO₂), 202°; **155** (*p*-NO₂), 198°.

Antibacterial activity : The compounds were subjected to *in vitro* screening by cup-plate agar diffusion method⁴ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* at two different concentrations of 25 and 50 µg ml⁻¹. The results of antibacterial tests indicated that 1,3-diaryl-2-(arylamino)propan-1,3-diones had considerable activity against all the three microorganisms. The activity varied with the nature of substituents as well as their position in the phenyl rings of the β-diketones. In case of 1-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-3-aryl-2-(arylamino)propan-1,3-diones, the activity against all the three microorganisms either remained unaltered or increased with a few exceptions. In the case of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl) analogues, activity against *S. aureus* decreased but increased against *E. coli*; however with *P. pyocyanea*, there was hardly any change.

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